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Performance of proven Cotton Varieties Demonstrated and Its economic return to producers in case of Afar Region, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Cotton is an important crop commodity in Ethiopian agriculture and source of cash for the producers, creates huge job opportunities and hard currency for the country through export of various products. Despite the importance of the crop; low productivity, poor access of improved varieties and extension services are some of the constraint of cotton production at middle Awash basin. This study was done to assess yield performance, gap and economic return of new cotton varieties (Werer-50 and Weyto-07) to the producers. A total of 90 cotton producers were participated in demonstration. Demonstrated Werer-50 variety has 16.429% to 15.60 %, while; Weyto-07 variety has 17.92% to 18.35% yield advantage at Amibara and Gewane districts, respectively. The benefit cost ratios for improved cotton variety was 2.02 and 1.71 birr for local deltapine-90. The result of benefit cost ratio indicated that the producers were obtained 2.02 birr for each birr invested on improved cotton varieties and 1.71 Birr for local check. In general, the demonstrated cotton varieties in the areas were shown significant impact on productivity and profitability. Therefore, the study recommends that; strengthen effective and efficient delivery of technological promotion methods such as capacity building and close extension support will be advised to reduce knowledge and productivity gaps and shortage of alternative proven cotton varieties in the study area.

Key words: Producers, Demonstration, Cotton Varieties, cost-benefit

1. INTRODUCTION

Cotton crop is deep-rooted in the history of Ethiopian agriculture. It is an important crop commodity in Ethiopian agriculture and the lives cotton farmers. It is source of cash for the growers and hard currency for the country through export of various products and creates huge job opportunities (Melesse *et al*, 2019 and NCRS 2016).

Ethiopia has an estimated area of 2.6 million hectares suitable for cotton production. Of this 65% or 1.69 million ha is found in high potential cotton producing areas of Awash, Omo, Ghibe, Wabi-Shebelle, Baro-Akobo, Blue Nile and Tekeze river basins. From the total land under cotton cultivation, 33% is cultivated by small holders, 45% by private farms and 22% are state-owned farms. But, Ethiopia shares only 5% of total cotton produced in Africa. Recently Ethiopia cultivates only 780,000 ha of the total suitable land for cotton production which account three percent and produces an average of 33,842.11 metric tons in the year 2000–2018 and earned an average of \$ 14,336,667 from export market in the last decade and employs about 52,754 smallholder farmers (Admassie, Seid, May, Megquier, & Moreland, 2015, ICAC, 2014) site by Melesse *et al*, 2019

However despite the importance of the crop on overall economic development in general and for textile industry specifically, cotton growers have faced different constraints. Low productivity, poor access of

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improved varieties, poor extension services and occurrence of unknown new pest and lack of mechanized cotton technologies are some of the constraint of cotton production (Melesse *et al*, 2019).

This is true for middle awash basin of Afar region; specifically in study areas (Amibara and Gewane districts) which is the major cotton producing district in the region. In the area producers use only one proven variety for more than 20 years. Most cotton producers' use unknown cotton seed which is genetically deteriorated and exposed to different pest and diseases. Due to this and others factors the production and productivity of the crop was low and leads producers to leave cotton production and look for other alternative crops.

To overcome the problem access to improved cotton varieties, Werer agricultural research center released newly improved cotton varieties: Werer-50 and weyto-07 the new cotton varieties currently promote to the end users through different technology promotion approach. With the objective of enhance diffusion and adoption of the technology to large number of producers then reducing the access, gap of productivity and increase profitability of producers. However, despite the verities were demonstrated to producers; yield performance, gap and profitability of the varieties were not evaluated and analyzed or the research result was not reported. Therefore, this research was done to evaluate the yield performance, gap and its economic return proven cotton varieties demonstrated at Afar region, Ethiopia.

Specific Objectives:-

- To evaluate yield performance of demonstrated proven cotton varieties
- To identify extension and technology gap of proven cotton varieties demonstrated.
- To analyze economic profitability of proven cotton for producers

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study areas

The study was done in middle wash basin at Amibara and Gewane districts of Afar region from 2018/19 to 2019/20 cropping seasons. The districts were selected purposively due to cotton production potential and high demand of the crop.

Amibara District is located in the Afar Regional State in north eastern parts of Ethiopia at geographic coordinates of 09°13'–09°30' N and 40°05'–40°25' E. The study area has dominated by plains, with a slope range of 0–8 % and altitude range from 665 to 815 m.a.s.l. (MoA 1997). The climate can generally be described as hot semiarid, with maximum and minimum temperatures varying from 25 to 42 °C and 15.2 to 23.5 °C, respectively, and an average annual rainfall of 560 mm (Worer Agro-meteorology Section (WAS), 2008). The major crop growing in the area is cotton, maize and onion.

Gewane district: is located in the Afar Regional State in north eastern parts Ethiopia at geographic coordinates of 10°9'59" N and 40°38'43" E. The study area has dominated by plains, with a slope range of 0–8 % and altitude of 618m.a.s.l. (CSA 2005). The climate can generally be described as hot semiarid, with maximum and minimum temperatures varying from 30 to 43 °C and 20.2 to 27.5 °C, respectively, and an average annual rainfall of 510 mm. The major crop growing in the area is cotton and maize.

2.2. Materials and implementation approaches

Cotton pre extension demonstration participants were selected with collaboration of districts agricultural office. In sum 108 demonstrations were conducted at two districts on an area of 37.5 ha.

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Implementation approaches

The following implementation approach was used while done demonstration research

- Trainings,
- Field visits, and
- Experience sharing and Field days were arranged and organized.

Participants' agro pastoral research groups were selected with the following criteria

- Willing to contribute the land,
- implement demonstration research in good quality,
- sufficient irrigation water source,
- Willing to share experience to others and access to all weather road

Materials used

- Werer-50 and Weyto-07 and local produced Deltapine-90 variety for check.
- Plot size 1ha/Agro pastorals

Recommended cotton production package used

- Improved cotton seed = 15-18 kg ha⁻¹
- Spacing adopted was 90 cm inter row and 20 cm intra row spacing.
- Irrigation frequency was given as 15 days interval after sowing

Weed management

- Hand weeding and hoeing operations on 15th, 35th, and 75th days after the crop emergences were conducted to keep the field weed free.

Pest management

- Integrated pest management was used to control pest and disease

Sowing date

- Sowing date from April 15 to 30

Soil type

- Loam alluvial and medium to high fertility status.

2.3. Farmers and agro pastorals variety preference and perception

Farmer's variety preference and perception toward demonstrated varieties were assessed through focus group discussion. Model producers, agricultural experts and development agents were involved. An agronomic performance (Fertile boll formation, boll size, and plant height and uniformity maturity) and yield variety was considered during discussion.

2.4. Data collected

Personal and socio-economic information of participant, yield, percentage yield advantage, producers' perception and variety preference and economic return of demonstrated varieties related data were collected and summarized.

2.5. Method of data analysis

Simple descriptive statistics and narrative explanation were used to analyze data by using excel and SPSS statistical software.

Percentage Yield advantage

Percentage Yield advantage = (yield of new variety (qt ha⁻¹) - yield of standard check (qt ha⁻¹))*100 ÷ yield of standard check (qt ha⁻¹)

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Profitability analysis

Commonly used method budgetary technique was used to evaluate profitability of new cotton variety demonstrated in the study area. Gross margin, net revenue and benefit cost ratio was used to computed the profitability of the crop. Gross margin (GM) is gross revenue excess of the total variable costs. Total variable cost is a summation of operational costs that vary with changes in scale of operation includes seed cost, chemicals cost, transport cost, labor cost and etc. whereas, fixed costs are depreciation cost of farm land. Farmers farm tool and labor cost was not considered in the study. Benefit cost ratio is the ratio of the gross return and total cost of the enterprise. The profitability statistics were specified and computed as follow (Eze and Nwibo, 2014 and Debertain, 2012):

Gross Margin (GM)

Gross Margin (GM) = Total Return (TR) - Total Variable Cost (TVC)

Profit

Profit = Gross Margin (GM) - Total Fixed Cost (TFC)

Cost-Benefit Ratio= Total Return (TR)/Total cost (TC)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Personal and Socioeconomic information of participants

A total of 90 small and large scale cotton producers having (91.1 male and 8.9% female) were participated in pre extension demonstration research from 2018/19 to 2019/20 cropping season. 55.5 % age composition active working group between 25 to 40 year. Minimum respondents 14.4%, belong to young (18-24) and 5.6%) old age group (>61). The education status of participants show that 81.1% of participants were read, write, primary and high school completed and 12.2% were diploma holders, 6.7% illiterate. Regarding to land holding 52.2% were small holders having an area less 20 ha and 47.8% were large scale cotton growers greater than 20 ha (**Table 1**). Data pertaining to experience in farming exerted that 55.6%, 38.9% and 5.6% were experienced more then 10, 6-10 and up to 5 year respectively. Result clearly showed that maximum respondents had long farming experience. However, 73.3% respondents never have linkage with extension agent. Poor linkage with extension agent could be one of the important factors that contribute to low adoption of improved varieties and production technologies.

Table 1 Personal and Socioeconomic profile

Profile of participants	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)	18-24	13	14.4
	25-40	50	55.6
	41-60	22	24.4
	>61	5	5.6
Education	Illiterate	6	6.7
	Read and write	37	41.1
	Primary school Completed	17	18.9
	High school completed	19	21.1
	Diploma(12+3) and above	11	12.2
Size of land holding	Small holder less then 20ha	47	52.2

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		Large scale above 21ha	43	47.8
Cotton production experience	Up to 5 year		5	5.6
	6 to 10 year		35	38.9
	Above ten year		50	55.6
Linkage with extension service	Frequency		4	4.4
	Occasionally		20	22.2
	Never		66	73.3
	Total		90	100.0

3.2. Yield and Yield Advantage of Demonstrated Varieties

The combined average yield of demonstrated cotton varieties of Weyto-07 and Werer-50 was higher as compared to average yield of Deltapine-90 in two year demonstration period. The combined mean average yield of Weyto-07 at both demonstration districts were showed nearly similar yield which account 34.19 to 34.45 qt ha⁻¹ with standard deviation 2.17 to 1.83 at Amibara and Gewane district, respectively. Whereas, Werer -50 variety was showed approximately 33.76 qt ha⁻¹ average yield at Amibara district and 33.65 qt ha⁻¹ at Gewane district with standard deviation 2.95 and 2.37, respectively. The average yield of local cheek at Amibara and Gewane were showed approximately equal yield that is 29 qt ha⁻¹. The demonstrated cotton varieties have 3 to 4 quintal yield advantage than local cheek. In others words Weyto-07 had 17.92% and 18.35% yield advantage over local check at Amibara and Gewane districts, respectively. While Werer-50 cotton variety had 16.42% and 15.60% yield advantage than local cheek at Amibara and Gewane districts, respectively (Table 4). The result of this study was indicated that the pre-extension demonstration of new cotton varieties have relatively better yield advantage at all demonstrated districts.

Percentage yield advantage of demonstrated varieties computed as follows;-

Percentage yield advantage = $\frac{\text{average (yield of new variety (qt ha}^{-1}) - \text{yield of standard check (qt ha}^{-1})) \times 100}{\text{average yield of standard check (qt ha}^{-1})}$

Table 4 Combined average and percentage yield difference of varieties

District	Varieties	Combined yield in qt ha ⁻¹			Std. Deviation	% yield difference or advantage
		Minimum	Maximum	Mean		
Amibara	Weyto 07	29.85	37.30	34.19	2.17	17.92
	Werer 50	26.35	38.00	33.76	2.95	16.42
	Check	23.85	33.88	29.00	2.79	
Gewane	Weyto 07	30.95	37.52	34.45	1.83	18.35
	Werer 50	30.30	37.43	33.65	2.37	15.60
	Check	22.89	34.48	29.11	3.42	

3.3. Farmers Variety preference

According to discussion held with focus group Weyto-07 variety was selected in the study areas for its good fertile boll formation, large boll size, and plant height and yield advantage. Whereas Weyto-07 variety has less uniform maturity than check which need second picking and time consuming.

While; Werer-50 variety also had better yield advantage than check at both demonstrated site, this variety was showed relatively better uniform maturity that has advantage of hand picking than Weyto-07. As a result Werer-50 variety was preferred next to Weyto- 07.

The local check (Deltapin-90) at producers hand was preferred as a last option because of its low yield, poor crop stand and non uniformity.

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According to focus group discussion; they preferred local check due to its resistance to pests but it showed genetical deterioration this is why the reason for low yield, poor crop stand and uniformity. However, it was more adopted in existing environment for more than two ten years. Therefore, breeders must search the way of restore its genetic capacity.

3.4. Profitability analysis

The gross returns cost of cultivation, net returns and benefit of cotton varieties were computed (Table 5). The cultivation of cotton using improved technologies was given higher net returns of 8,010.00 Birr ha⁻¹ than local check variety. The benefit cost ratios of cotton for improved technologies and local check were showed 2.02 and 1.71birr, respectively. The result of benefit cost ratio was indicated that the producer obtained 2.02 birr for each birr invested to the production of improved cotton varieties and 1.71birr for check variety,. This was due to higher yields of improved variety than local check.

Table 5. Profitability analysis of demonstrated varieties

	Location (middle awash)	
	New variety	check
	Werer 50 and Weyto 07	Delta pain- 90
Av. Yield Qt ha -1	34.45	29.11
Market Price of row cotton / Qutl.	1,500.00	1,500.00
Total Return (TR) in ETB	51,675.00	43,665.00
Variable Cost (VC)		
Seed cost	626.20	626.2
Urea	1,500.00	1,500.00
Chemicals	6000	6000
Labor cost		
land preparation, plowing, disking, rigging	3,500.00	3,500.00
Planting and sowing	750	750
Field irrigating	2000	2,000.00
weeding	1,500.00	1,500.00
chemical spray	1000	1000
Picking/harvesting/	3,200.00	3,200.00
Total Variable Cost(TVC)	20,076.20	20,076.20
Fixed cost		
Cost of land /ha/season	5,500.00	5,500.00
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)	5,500.00	5,500.00
Total Cost(TC)		
TC= TVC+TFC	25,576.00	25,576.20
Gross margin		
GM= TR-TVC	31,598.80	23,580.80
Profit		
Profit = GM- TFC	26,098.80	18,088.80
Benefit cost ratio	2.02	1.71

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3.5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In general, the demonstrated new cotton varieties were shown significant impact on productivity and economic return for the producers. Therefore, strengthen effective and efficient delivery of technological promotion methods such as capacity building, close extension support and teaching should be advised. To reduce the production gaps, shortage of alternative cotton varieties and knowledge gap in the study areas continuous support will be need for producers from all relevant stakeholders and national cotton research teams. On top of these breeders should be considered farmers preference criteria during the development of new varieties to save time and resources then fast technology promotion and adoption.

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